

Urban Relief

Utrecht Pilot Report

D4.6

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Short description	The D4.6 Utrecht Pilot Report describes the progress and activities of the Utrecht approach to mitigating heat stress through private greening and active community management. It describes the findings and the expected next steps of the campaigns in the Utrecht project 'Green Neighbourhood Cool Neighbourhood'.
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Table of Contents

Table of Contents.....	4
Acronyms.....	5
List of Figures	6
List of Tables	7
Executive Summary	8
Background on the Urban ReLeaf Project and City Pilots	9
1 Heat Stress Campaign.....	10
1.1 Context and Objectives.....	10
1.2 Design and Implementation	13
1.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used	18
1.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection.....	22
1.5 Findings and Reflections	30
1.6 Recommendations and Future Steps.....	39
2 Thermal Perceptions Campaign.....	40
2.1 Context and Objectives.....	40
2.2 Design and Implementation	40
2.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used	43
2.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection.....	44
2.5 Findings and Reflections	45
2.6 Recommendations and Future Steps.....	45
References	46
Appendices.....	47
Appendix A: User Agreement for participants Green Neighbourhood, Cool Neighbourhood	47
Appendix B: Second and final versions of the perception survey.....	48

Acronyms

CITYUTR	Municipality of Utrecht
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
ICCS	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
IIASA	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
KNMI	Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wide Area Network
NMU	Utrecht Nature and Environment Federation
PROVUTR	Province of Utrecht
RIVM	National Institute for Public Health and the Environment
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SECU	Utrecht Educational Centre Foundation
TRH	Temperature and Relative Humidity
UHI	Urban Heat Island Effect
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel

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List of Figures

Figure 1. Annual average temperature from the Bilt measuring station.	12
Figure 2. Heat stress campaign promotion overview.	15
Figure 3. The UR cargo bike during the Climate Conference 2024 in Nieuwegein, Netherlands.	16
Figure 4. Perceived temperature on a hot day in the Ondiep neighbourhood.	19
Figure 5. Visualization of the TRH data in the Digital Twin.	21
Figure 6. Overview of TRH data transfer and visualizations.	22
Figure 7. Impressions of the kick-off meetings.	23
Figure 8. Impressions of the activities for the <i>Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt</i> community.	24
Figure 9. An example of a message in the WhatsApp community group: a request to start measuring in Kanaleneiland.	25
Figure 10. An example of a message in the WhatsApp community group: a request to start measuring in Zuilen.	26
Figure 11. An example of a news item in the WhatsApp community group.	27
Figure 12. Impressions of the activities for involving vulnerable groups.	29
Figure 13. Spatial coverage of sensor measurements in Utrecht on a log scale.	30
Figure 14. Amount of data by device. (Counting a pair of relative humidity and temperature as one observation and ignoring the button records).	31
Figure 15. All temperature measurements throughout the days, with the median line and the 25 and 75 quartiles for each hour shown.	32
Figure 16. Example of a trip with dubious GPS records based on erratic measurements at the end of a trip, with speed in km/h.	33
Figure 17. Graph showing the distribution of participants considering taking greening measures.	35
Figure 18. Graph showing which specific greening measures participants are considering.	35
Figure 19. The promotional leaflet used to draw attention to the survey.	41
Figure 20. Overview of the approach to the Thermal Perceptions Campaign.	42
Figure 21. Map of the 17 survey sites identified as cool and hot spots.	43
Figure 22. Thermal Perceptions Campaign survey activities.	44

List of Tables

Table 1. Overview hotspots and coolspots based on button presses. 33

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Executive Summary

Mitigating heat stress through private greening and active community management

In 2024 and 2025, the Municipality of Utrecht, the Province of Utrecht, and the Utrecht Nature and Environment Federation carried out two citizen science campaigns with the name *Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt*, (Green Neighbourhood, Cool Neighbourhood) to better understand heat stress in vulnerable neighbourhoods:

1. **Heat Stress Campaign:** 160 residents formed a community and measured temperature, humidity, and (dis)comfort in four green-poor neighbourhoods of Utrecht (Ondiep, Zuilen, Rivierenwijk, Kanaleneiland) during the summer months of 2024 and 2025.
2. **Thermal Perceptions Campaign:** research into thermal perceptions conducted via on-site surveys of previously identified “cool and hot spots” in summer 2025.

An inclusive approach was adopted, actively engaging vulnerable groups, such as residents with limited language skills or financial resources, in data collection and in discussions on potential solutions. This ensured that diverse perspectives were represented throughout the process.

Key insights:

- Neighbourhoods are, on average, 4–5 °C warmer than the Bilt monitoring station, especially at night.
- Greenery and shade demonstrably reduce heat stress; paved streets remain hotspots.
- Residents marked 239 hotspots and 41 cool spots; interviews link measurement data to perception.
- Data confirm KNMI models and offer new opportunities for analysing humidity and social factors.
- The use of the sensor and app was not yet optimal, which was frustrating for users. Participants remained engaged thanks to social cohesion.

Impact and next steps:

- Residents are developing concrete greening and shading plans (pergolas, façade gardens, tree pits).
- Subsidy applications and creative projects are being prepared to share insights widely.
- In 2026, it will be explored whether the existing *Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt* community can be mobilized for other greening and cooling initiatives.

Conclusion:

The aggregated data from the citizen science project *Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt*, as part of Urban ReLeaf, offer valuable insights for research and urban planning. While individual-level data from the app and sensors are not yet fully suitable for use with vulnerable groups, the project’s community-building efforts have strengthened social cohesion and fostered a sense of agency in climate awareness and greening initiatives. These outcomes support municipal climate adaptation strategies and contribute to creating a fairer, cooler, and more resilient living environment.

Background on the Urban ReLeaf Project and City Pilots

Urban ReLeaf promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address urgent climate issues and support innovations that enable more just and green urban transitions. The project addresses the challenges of increasing environmental stresses in urban areas, accentuated inequalities in access to high-quality greenspace, lack of suitable data for planning and decision making as well as inclusion in public participation in science and research.

The main objectives of Urban ReLeaf are to:

- Understand current data ecosystem and urban greening and participation policies in six pilot cities and co-develop opportunities for citizen science and citizen participation to complement existing practices.
- Mobilise and empower local communities in issues of public interest surrounding urban green infrastructure and environmental stewardship.
- Support the long-term inclusion of active and passive data from citizens within official data streams for urban monitoring, planning and innovation in public policy.
- Encourage knowledge exchange and training across relevant actors beyond the six pilot cities by establishing a community of practice and an accelerator programme.
- Offer flexible and innovative ways of governance that can underpin inclusive green urban planning in support of the European Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In pursuit of urban climate resilience, six Urban ReLeaf pilot cities co-create participatory, and data-driven innovations to democratise urban greenspace monitoring and the wider policy making process.

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1 Heat Stress Campaign

To understand 'heat stress' in Utrecht and to explore how to involve residents in this topic, a citizen science approach was rolled out. The Utrecht approach concentrates in 4 neighbourhoods: Ondiep, Zuilen, Kanaleneiland and Rivierenwijk. Inhabitants of these city quarters were engaged into communities that do citizen science on local heat-stress during the summer months of 2024 and 2025. As part of the *Green Neighbourhood, Cool Neighbourhood* campaign, participants used sensors to collect observations on temperature, humidity, and heat stress during walks through the neighbourhood. These temperature and relative humidity (TRH) sensors were distributed during a kick-off event, and additional activities were organised to make this topic discussable within the community.

1.1 Context and Objectives

Understanding heat stress

Understanding heat stress in green-deprived neighbourhoods is the leading topic for the Utrecht City pilot. This is done by a citizen science approach, creating a shared knowledge base from within the neighbourhood communities. Follow-up steps are action planning, connecting to existing policy instruments, and possibly creating a longer-term citizen science data eco-system.

Utrecht neighbourhoods

The topic of heat stress is closely related to the historical development of the city, to how the build environment and its populations developed. Some neighbourhoods from before (ca. 1910 > mid1930s) and after the Second World War (late 1950s and '60s) were built for functionality and for quick upscaling of the housing capacity. That resulted in areas with a rather monotonous stock of apartment buildings, or street-level houses that are less attractive by today's standards (small gardens, less floorspace, badly insulated). What these neighbourhoods also have in common is a lack of attractive public green space, which subsequently leads to heat-island problems during the hot summer months.

The Utrecht pilots concentrate on 4 of such neighbourhoods: **Ondiep, Zuilen, Kanaleneiland** and **Rivierenwijk**. We engaged the inhabitants of these city quarters into communities that do citizen science on local heat-stress during the summer months of 2024 and 2025.

Citizen science

Science is an approach to expand, enhance and test the existing knowledge and understanding of the world around us. The professional scientific community follows strict methodology, tests hypotheses, (re)builds theories to explain phenomena, and works on empirical replicable observations and analyses. Progressive outcomes and insights are peer-reviewed and published. Generally, there is a high level of trust from society in the knowledge base that comes from science. At the same time, science and data-gathering (often time- and capacity-intensive) cannot cover every aspect of our world and environments. That is where citizen science can effectively step in. For topics that are relevant for citizens, but not of immediate relevance for public authorities or science, data collection by citizens greatly increases the knowledge base for a geographic area, and a variety of themes. Environmental themes seem typical: water quality, air quality, biodiversity, precipitation, and heat (stress).

Citizen science should not be a simple matter of added observation capacity. As science goes beyond just the systematic collection of data, citizen science is ideally truly scientific: it is a systematic approach to understanding physical and social phenomena. It should start with a question (what do we think is happening here?), an idea about the necessary information that is lacking to answer that question and then a structured proposal to do measurements and observations. Often, getting to the most effective question to follow up on, requires another step of preparation: becoming aware that a sometimes unconsciously perceived problem (extreme heat in/near your home, for example) deserves a good question (why is it so hot here? what can we do about it?). That is why the 'awareness raising' is an essential part of the Utrecht pilots, even before people are ready to proceed as 'citizen scientists'.

But citizen science does not stop there: data only becomes 'information' after systematic analysis, and information only becomes something useful when its implications are discussed. It is exactly those extra steps that make citizen science go beyond what the scientific community has to offer to society. Defining jointly within a community 'what the question is' is already providing social 'agency' (for example: how does summer heat behave in our neighbourhoods? when does that lead to actual heat stress? what situations do we already know where heat stress is lessened by physical features or perhaps behaviour? and if we understand that: what actions can we take to improve our environment?). Then systematically gathering data and transforming those into information is the next step into becoming 'an authority' instead of a joint cloud of opinions about the research topic. The discussion that happens next does require moderation but is now based not merely on top-down/external 'expert knowledge' or varying personal opinions. A 'shared knowledge base' and joint 'fact finding' are crucial here, on a factual as well as a social level. Having become 'experts' themselves, the citizen science communities can focus the discussion on application of that knowledge and action.

Expert knowledge, climate policy, understanding green/cool places

The climatic measurements and modelling for Utrecht were already quite extensive, done by the Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI) for example, and the Institute for Environment and Health (RIVM). That information shows a general 'heat trap' effect of summer warmth in the urban environment, sometimes beyond 5°.

A study that shows clearly the effect of the urban heat island effect (UHI) was done by KNMI for the city of Utrecht revealing several causes for the development of UHIs (KNMI, 2010). One of the most important appears to be the city's geometry, often expressed as the Sky View Factor or the ratio of building height to street width. The study done in 2010 on a specific traffic route shows a UHI of more than 5 degrees Celsius. The article suggests it could be more on other traffic routes.

KNMI also makes information available [on their website](#) of the annual average temperature (Figure 1) in the Bilt, a measuring station nearby Utrecht. Modelling also shows local variations as interpretations of the physical features in neighbourhoods (buildings, trees, water, etc.).

Figure 1. Annual average temperature from the Bilt measuring station.

The [Climate Adaptation Vision](#) of the Municipality of Utrecht sets the scene for development towards a climate-proof city, able to deal with water downpours and heatwaves. Greening the ‘stony’ urban environment up to 40% of the public space is part of that policy, as are displayed visually in [Utrecht on the Map](#) and the [Climate Effect Atlas](#).

We know that ‘green’ (being tree shadow, and also water and general not too short vegetation on ground level) is an effective way to stabilize the urban climate (Kluck et al., 2020). At the same time, greening the existing city is a challenge, because of fierce competition for space among several urban functions, and because of the costs in realisation plus maintenance. Generally bringing ‘green’ up to 40% everywhere might be the goal, but prioritisation in space and time is essential. That requires really understanding

- how ‘heat’ behaves in- and outside our houses on street-level.
- how ‘green’ works as a mitigator.
- how people actually perceive heat, appreciate ‘green’, and
- how they make use of their own neighbourhoods.
- how ‘cool’ do the streets need to be during hot weeks, when children go to school, or elderly people go shopping?
- what unique features do ‘cool spots’ (presumably also ‘green places’) have in order to really function as cherished places near home, where people go to ‘be outside’ in a comfortable way?

The questions above cannot be answered by expert knowledge and policy implementation alone. It is the intimate knowledge of people and communities in a city’s neighbourhoods that answer these questions. And where citizen science can ‘fill in the blanks’ when even the local people do not have the concrete answers yet.

1.2 Design and Implementation

Organisation & approach

The province of Utrecht (regional government) and the municipality of Utrecht (local government) have developed and operated the Utrecht pilot for Urban ReLeaf together, as full project partners/beneficiaries. Early on, they realised that neighbourhood pilots with community building, stakeholder engagement and support would be beyond their expertise and capacity. Additionally, these government organisations would possibly express a much too top-down approach to these neighbourhoods, while a grassroots/bottom-up participatory approach is needed. The experienced local non-governmental organisation the *Nature and Environment Federation Utrecht* (Natuur en Milieufederatie Utrecht, NMU) was contracted to organise the community management and pilot campaigns. The province of Utrecht has already been collaborating extensively with NMU on the implementation of various citizen science projects, under the name 'Samen Meten Utrecht' (Measuring Together Utrecht). This proved to be an effective choice and is recommended for future upscaling initiatives.

Together with NMU and neighbourhood organisations with their key figures, we aimed to shape the campaign through an Asset-Based Community Development. This is an approach to strengthening communities that focuses on what is already present, rather than on what is missing. The idea is to build on the strengths, talents, resources, and networks that exist within a community, instead of focusing solely on problems or deficiencies. In the beginning of the campaign recruitment of participants were tried to find through key figures in the neighbourhood. This had limited success. These people lack capacity and resources. They are, however, an important source of local knowledge.

Collaboration with the neighbourhood initiatives in the spring of 2024 was somewhat challenging, mainly due to other priorities and/or absences caused by illness. From the municipality and the province, together with NMU and University of Dundee, an inclusive communication and recruitment campaign was launched with a core message developed with the neighbourhood initiatives, including Turkish and Arabic translations, no government logos, but instead local associations and recognizable images created and used. The goal was to specifically reach the target group that is more distant from the government.

Translated core message: Keep it green, stay cool

Urbanization, hot summers, drought, and heavy rain challenge us, but together we tackle the challenge of staying healthy and happy. The Municipality of Utrecht joins hands with residents, the Province of Utrecht, the Nature and Environment Federation of Utrecht, and five other European cities: Riga, Dundee, Mannheim, Cascais, and Athens. Residents in Utrecht explore the experience of heat in the city by collecting data and together we seek green solutions that provide cooling. With this, we aim for more awareness about heat and the positive effect of a green city. Because a green neighbourhood is a cool neighbourhood!

The Utrecht pilot went one step farther still: while we made it clear that it was part of a European cooperation of 6 cities, funded through the EU Urban ReLeaf project, Utrecht started the pilot as the "Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt" campaign. Using this 'Green Neighbourhood, Cool Neighbourhood' approach in communication made the pilots more accessible and 'local', which helped to attract attention and reach participants from a wider range of backgrounds.

To reach 'vulnerable groups' a translation function to other languages was added to the website *Samen Meten Utrecht - Koele Buurt Groene Buurt*. This function didn't affect participant recruitment. However, it proved to be helpful to have information available in another language when interviewing participants through Stichting CQ (refugees).

Utrecht used the term 'hittehelden' (heat heroes) to refer to residents who, on their own initiative but as a group, want to map heat and make their neighbourhood greener.

As mentioned, the Urban ReLeaf Utrecht pilot covered two seasons (2024 and 2025), during which we explored several parallel topics. These topics feed back into the larger Urban ReLeaf objectives and learning themes:

- Understanding (citizen science) data collection, management and analysis, and understanding how 'data driven' policymaking and implementation actually are.
- Understanding how to mobilize and empower local communities for citizen science, as well as for social purposes.

In the end, the goal is to reach a broad set of neighbourhood inhabitants, including 'vulnerable groups'. And by engaging them, we hope they understand the topic of heat-stress better, have experienced the practice of citizen science, and that we have given them action perspective towards positive changes in their living environment.

- Understanding how citizen science can become an integral part of a city's data ecosystem and monitoring.
- Understanding what approaches, processes and technologies work and are necessary for the above points to be successful.

During the pilot seasons, the Urban ReLeaf project 'full consortium meetings' (online) provided a platform for sharing experience and evaluating approaches. Experiences from the Season 1 summer campaigns in the different partner cities were shared and taken up to shape the campaigns for 2025. These shared insights, together with these pilot reports, should give the basis for establishing a community of practice and an accelerator programme.

Under the umbrella of the regional citizen science practice centre *Samen Meten Utrecht*, the campaign was carried out. An infrastructure for organising multiple citizen science projects was already in place. *Samen Meten Utrecht* also focused on participant recruitment through its own channels. The campaign materials (Figure 2) featured local imagery, used simple language, and were offered in multiple languages (including Turkish and Arabic) and both digitally and physically.

Figure 2. Heat stress campaign promotion overview.

Local neighbourhood organisations put up posters and handed out flyers and postcards to recruit participants. They also used their app groups to reach interested local residents. The call was posted on the BuurtNatuur030 platform, and the municipality of Utrecht ultimately issued a press release.

The province and municipality communicated about the new citizen science project through their own channels and at conferences and seminars, including a visit with the cargo bike (Figure 3) to the Climate Conference in June 2024.

Figure 3. The UR cargo bike during the Climate Conference 2024 in Nieuwegein, Netherlands.

2024 Summer Campaign

The 2024 summer recruitment campaign engaged 326 inhabitants in the 4 neighbourhoods and managed to get 103 participants in the actual 'citizen science communities'. These communicated through WhatsApp groups, kept each other motivated and helped each other with technical problems. This was all actively coordinated by NMU, and it was a great success in keeping the group motivated, up to date, and connected. Of the wearable TRH sensors provided by the Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) technical partner of the Urban ReLeaf consortium, a 103 were used in the field in July, August and September. Coupled to a dedicated smartphone 'EcoPulse' app, these collected over 45.000 measurements.

During the first measurement summer, hardly any questions were asked about the socio-economic background of participants. This was partly because we were not consciously focused on it. Moreover, given the technical knowledge required to participate, the background of the group did not seem relevant for measuring temperature, humidity, and heat spots.

For the next measurement season, we did take important lessons forward. We aimed to approach target groups differently and to involve key figures and ambassadors (current participants) to help recruit new participants. For this, we used the strategy blueprints. In addition, we expanded our narrative and clearly explained why we want to work with vulnerable groups. This helped us collect more personal data from participants, for example for the inclusivity tracker. The Urban ReLeaf consortium (lead partners at the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA)) carried out the first analysis of the collected

data in early 2025. The preliminary results confirmed our expectations: heat stress effects in certain areas, relatively higher temperatures in built-up zones, and a prolonged temperature rise during summer nights. This analysis also provided valuable insights into data collection and analysis: how to maximize our community efforts with TRH sensors and how to process the data to uncover underlying patterns.

These initial conclusions have been incorporated into the campaign planning for 2025. The summer campaign was partly an extended continuation of the first year, aimed at gaining a better understanding of hot and cool spots in Utrecht neighbourhoods, building on the lessons from Season 1. In addition, we aimed to achieve better representation of diverse residents in discussions and possibly in local heat stress measurements. Thanks to adjustments in the smartphone applications, the existing data protection impact assessment (DPIA) is now also suitable for working with young people (13+).

2025 Summer campaign

With the lessons learned from 2024, we have divided the 2025 measurement summer into three different parts, that together serve the Urban ReLeaf goals and lead to a better understanding of heat stress management in the public space.

1. Second TRH Measurement Campaign

- Conduct a second TRH measurement campaign with the four neighbourhood communities, in which participants will carry out missions with their boxes several times during the summer months. In addition, they will be able to attend activities (such as neighbourhood safaris).
- Improve data collection based on lessons learned from Season 1 (increase the density of measurements at locations and times + add cool spots to the app)
- Arrive at usable conclusions about temperature, humidity, and heat spots, by organising data-meetings with the participants

Result: In 2025, 61 participants took part in the general campaign. 50% of the 2024 participants also took part in 2025. For the community, neighbourhood safaris were organised, and NMU set up a mission to encourage participants to walk at specific times (late afternoon–evening) and locations (parks). Compared to 2024, there were fewer participants, but the number of observations was similar.

At the end of October, Martin Hofer (IIASA) presented his data analysis, after which residents themselves proposed initiatives to make the neighbourhood greener.

2. Engaging Specific 'Vulnerable' Target Groups

- Now that the citizen science approach is established, we focused on involving diverse and vulnerable groups
- We do not name the groups but worked with organisations that collaborated with these groups to organise activities, of which measuring with a sensor is a small part.
- Use key figures and ambassadors to help reach these target groups.

Result: In addition to heat data and experiential insights, Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt actively engaged participants in 2025 who are often underrepresented in climate policy but are crucial

for their knowledge and experience. Together with Globe College in Kanaleneiland, guest lectures were held, and measurements were taken with students on the hottest day of the year. In collaboration with the Stichting Educatief Centrum Utrecht (SECU), a measurement activity was organised in Kanaleneiland. Furthermore, a master's student in New Media and Digital Culture organised a “heat crawl” for students—a combination of a neighbourhood walk with a climate expert, measurements, a pub quiz, and pizza. The common thread in all these gatherings was talking about climate and everyone's experiences, complemented by collecting new data.

3. Enriching Measurement Data with Perception Data

- Gain insight into how residents experience and use ‘hot’ and ‘cool’ spots in their neighbourhoods.
- Complement technical measurements with perception data (see Chapter 2: Thermal Perceptions Campaign).

1.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used

Neighbourhoods

The 4 neighbourhoods Ondiep, Zuilen, Kanaleneiland and Rivierenwijk were chosen for their specific development history and resulting structure and social composition (see: 1.1 Context and Objectives). We engaged the inhabitants of these city quarters into communities that do citizen science on local heat-stress during the summer months of 2024 and 2025

That must lead to better understanding the causes and effects of heat-stress, and the role that green spaces play in the comfort of the local living environment. Additionally, we learned about working with local communities and inclusion of local vulnerable population groups, integrating technological tools in citizen science, dealing with data-management and privacy issues and the governance needed to bring citizen science to actual policy measures.

And from the perspective of heat-stress, it is the public space that stands out as ‘stony’: streets with extensive pavements for (auto)mobility and parking, limited green spaces, often with streets that are too narrow for additional trees, and large apartment buildings that together act as ‘heat traps’ during hotter summer days.

The areas in the Utrecht City pilot are relatively stony and hot. This can be seen on the [map of perceived temperature on a hot day](#). An example of this in Figure 4 illustrates the perceived temperature on a hot day in the Ondiep neighbourhood.

Figure 4. Perceived temperature on a hot day in the Ondiep neighbourhood.

This relative unattractiveness is reflected in the composition of the population there, with more social housing, higher percentages of poverty and an unequal share of people from a (former) migrant worker background. History, housing, public-space and population lead to diverse 'vulnerabilities' in such neighbourhoods. The vulnerabilities of the neighbourhoods can be seen through the website [Dashboard - Klimateffectatlas](#). For each neighbourhood it is possible to see information on social vulnerability to heat.

After the 2024 evaluation with the participants, it became clear that there was a wish to compare the data with a neighbourhood that is greener and has a higher socio-economic status.

TRH sensors

In 2024, two types of sensors were used to measure temperature and relative humidity. These TRH sensors were specifically designed and produced by ICCS, a partner of Urban ReLeaf. The sensor has a plastic housing of 7x7 cm, with openings to allow air to reach the sensor inside. The interface is simple, featuring an LED indicator light for variable status information and a button for basic settings (resetting) and marking special locations where a participant perceives discomfort. The casing also contains a battery and USB-C port for charging, a transmitter (Bluetooth or long range wide area network (LoRaWAN)), the actual TRH sensors, a GPS unit, and a processing unit with memory. Each sensor has a unique ID code. Sensors automatically register when moved and then connect to GPS satellites. After that, the sensor starts measuring TRH data at 20-second intervals. TRH data and interactively indicated locations, linked to GPS positions, are temporarily stored in the sensor until uploaded to a smartphone or LoRaWAN network.

Two types of sensors:

- **Bluetooth sensors**

These sensors connect to a smartphone and enable interactive communication with the sensor and its output via the 'EcoPulse' app (ICCS). Pairing the sensor with the app must be done before measuring and with instructions provided.

- **LoRa sensors**

These sensors connect to the local long-range network. They collect the same data (Temperature, Relative Humidity, and discomfort), but the output cannot be viewed at an individual level.

Aggregated data from both types of sensors can be viewed through an anonymized display (geographical hexagon level) on the [ICCS website](#) and via the [Digital Twin](#).

Number of sensors delivered in 2024:

- 160 Bluetooth TRH sensors + EcoPulse smartphone app
- 10 LoRa TRH sensors

Number of sensors delivered in 2025:

- 110 Bluetooth TRH sensors + EcoPulse smartphone app
- 10 LoRa TRH sensors

The DPIA¹ agreement allowed anonymous sensor data to be shared with the project database (via both types of sensors).

EcoPulse app

This ICCS project partner developed smartphone app (iOS and Android) went through several iterations during the two pilot campaign summers. In its final version it allowed a specific sensor to be paired to the app, the users could actively start a 'measuring mission' (although the sensor would start measuring anyway, when movement was detected, together with outside GPS reception). The walked routes and its measurements would be visible to the user (but not to everyone else). The data produced by the sensor would be uploaded through the smartphone app to the database server of the ICCS project partner. Because these were not the data collected by the smartphone sensors (GPS, or anything else), this is the GDPR-proof approach, as agreed in the DPIA.

Upon registration, users were invited to (anonymously) answer some basic socio-demographic questions. This would feed into the general image of participation, with social statistics analysed by the project partners at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB).

¹ Data protection impact assessment (DPIA). A DPIA is an instrument for mapping the privacy risks of a data processing operation beforehand. To ensure that the organisation can take measures to mitigate these risks.

Digital Twin

The Utrecht Digital Twin is an interactive 3D model that captures everything from buildings and parks to underground infrastructure. It's a living data platform where city officials, researchers, and residents are collaborating to visualise changes and assess environmental impacts before implementation.

Utrecht has already integrated the Digital Twin into several projects. The neighbourhood climate data collected through Urban ReLeaf appears directly in the model (Figure 5), creating Utrecht's first comprehensive heat map and climate adaptation planning. Additionally, the model connects above ground plans with below ground constraints by linking 3D underground data with urban development. This isn't just data collection, it's informing where the city plants trees, installs cooling infrastructure, and prioritising green space development.

To protect privacy, the data is visualised in 100-metre hexagons as seen in Figure 6. When you click on a hexagon with your mouse, a visualisation of the temperature, humidity or discomfort level appears.

Figure 5. Visualization of the TRH data in the Digital Twin.

Figure 6. Overview of TRH data transfer and visualizations.

1.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection

Citizen science for neighbourhood communities, vulnerable groups, & residents

The Utrecht campaigns engaged various groups of residents, all of which are subgroups within the four pilot neighbourhoods. This approach reflects the diverse aspects of the Urban ReLeaf objectives: citizen science using technological tools, reaching specific target groups, and preparing policy interventions through better local understanding.

Neighbourhood communities & measuring heat data

In 2024 and 2025, a total of 160 enthusiastic participants from the four Utrecht pilot neighbourhoods became involved in the *Green Neighbourhood*, *Cool Neighbourhood* community.

Both measurement summer began with kick-off events for participants to learn more about the campaign and the delivery of the sensors (Figure 7). Participants were also asked to sign a user agreement (Appendix A: User Agreement for participants Green Neighbourhood, Cool Neighbourhood). Alderman Suzanne Schilderman from the municipality of Utrecht attended one of these kick-off events to talk about the major challenges facing the city, with a focus on climate adaptation. She discussed the importance of cooperation with residents and the cooling effects of greening. ICCS was also present to provide guidance on connecting smartphones to the sensors.

Figure 7. Impressions of the kick-off meetings.

It was not mandatory, but during the campaign months of July, August and September, the participants were asked to complete at least 10 missions. A mission consists of a walk in the neighbourhoods of at least 10 minutes. As a thank you and in exchange for returning the sensor, participants received a voucher worth €40 per person.

In addition, more events were organised for the community (Figure 8): 3 façade gardens workshops in 2024 and 4 Neighbourhood Safari's in 2024 and 2025. During the Winter months after the campaign, two data events were organised around the topics of 'the first results', 'heat stress', and 'from data to action'.

Figure 8. Impressions of the activities for the *Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt* community.

Effective use of WhatsApp community feature

One of the most successful strategies was leveraging the WhatsApp Community functionality. NMU served as the community manager and used this platform to maintain easy and accessible communication with participants. Initially, interactions focused primarily on resolving technical challenges. In the second year, the approach evolved: participants were assigned specific “missions” to collect data at designated times and locations (Figure 9 and Figure 10). The platform also facilitated seamless communication about upcoming events (Figure 11) and enabled participants to share information and experiences with one another, fostering a sense of collaboration and engagement within the community.

Figure 9. An example of a message in the WhatsApp community group: a request to start measuring in Kanaleneiland.

Figure 10. An example of a message in the WhatsApp community group: a request to start measuring in Zuilen.

Figure 11. An example of a news item in the WhatsApp community group.

These neighbourhood communities formed the core of the citizen science effort with data collection through Urban ReLeaf TRH sensors: understanding heat stress, hot- and cool places in the direct living environments. Working with the communities also provided valuable insights about community management, the link to policy implementation and the link between citizen science and action-planning.

Vulnerable groups & understanding heat stress

Despite the deliberate communication strategy, in 2024 we did not sufficiently engage participants from vulnerable groups in the four neighbourhoods. In 2025, the Utrecht team aimed to reach 30–40% of participants from the vulnerable target groups mentioned in the Grant Agreement: young people, students, and women with a migration background. This mainly concerns people with poor health, children (<5), older adults (65+), and people living at or below the social minimum, as they are vulnerable to heat. They are less able to protect themselves against climate change and therefore face a greater risk of harm. They also tend to take less responsibility for addressing these changes themselves. The reason we focus on young people, students, and migrant women is because we want to explore how to effectively reach vulnerable groups and share their insights, possibly through the application of citizen science (social engagement). These groups are also seen as catalysts for change.

Ethical reflection

Why do we consider migrant women vulnerable? Approaching this group was not about physical vulnerability, such as sensitivity to heat, but about social and communicative factors: this group is often hard to reach. This makes it difficult to ask about their background. Moreover, the question “Do you feel vulnerable?” is uncomfortable and can be perceived as stigmatizing.

The Utrecht team therefore posed a fundamental question: should you even carry out a project like Urban ReLeaf with people considered vulnerable, and what is the purpose? Or is it better to focus on frontrunners? Given the limited reliability and immaturity of the sensor technology, it is not appropriate to involve vulnerable groups directly.

An alternative could have been to use the first year to engage a broader or less vulnerable target group. This provides valuable insights, allows for refining the approach, and ensures continuity of participation. In the second year, you can work more with specifically groups, as you have a better understanding of what is feasible and desirable.

Advice from VUB was to target young people aged 13–16, but not younger than 13 due to additional privacy concerns. VUB also recommended focusing on a narrow age range within the youth target group, for example, 15–16-year-olds rather than 13–16. This way, the group can be reached more effectively. Regarding privacy, European regulations for releasing data for young people under 16 are complex but still possible.

Activities

The organised events were mostly one-off meetings, emphasizing finding the best approach and the right form of interaction. The TRH sensors and the aspect of “data collection for citizen science” were introduced. However, the content of the sessions focused more on introducing the concept of urban heat stress and developing a shared understanding of causes, effects, and solutions. A variety of activities for different audiences, including vulnerable groups, were organised and facilitated (Figure 12). Among these audiences were:

- *Young people*
In collaboration with the partner Globe and the secondary school Globe College (Kanalenieiland), the existing UHIE lesson program has been expanded to include measurements with a TRH sensor. Due to the school's profile and the neighbourhood in which it is located, the participants are from the vulnerable target group. A guest lecture on climate and Urban ReLeaf was given by Moritz Harzenetter. Additionally, 15 students collected on July the 1st (one of the hottest days) data by themselves. After an introduction and pairing the sensor with the app, they walked through the neighbourhood in groups of 2 to 3 people and measured temperature and humidity. Using other sensors, they were able to measure surface temperature. Finally, the survey on heat perception was completed at the Marco Poloplein.
- *Migrant women*
Although we did not focus on migrant women, but rather on groups in the neighbourhoods that are less represented and often engaged with topics other than climate or heat, we did seek collaboration with Stichting SECU². SECU (Educational Center Foundation Utrecht) encourages, among other things, bringing women from different cultures together. They organise activities to prevent women from becoming socially isolated. On July 24th 2025, 11 migrant women attended an event organised by SECU and NMU. Specific subject was the difference between experiencing heat in their country of origin and the Netherlands. Dealing with the heat in the Netherlands

² Stichting SECU provides support and guidance to pupils, students, and adults in their education. The foundation includes an education centre specialized in this field. Stichting SECU is not only there for young people but also for adults, women, men, parents, and all other individuals and institutions that need advice or support in the areas of education and well-being. To achieve this, Stichting SECU offers various projects and activities.

they said was less easy because of the high humidity. Of the eleven attendees, eight migrants remained engaged with other activities.

- *University students*

In Kanaleneiland, on August 19 the ‘Heat crawl’ was organised in cooperation with the Utrecht University and NMU. An evening with beer, pizza and measurements was the result. Twelve international students attended this activity. Eight students enjoyed measuring and continued collecting data following the event.

Approximately 60–70% of the participants remained involved in Green Neighbourhood and Cool Neighbourhood after these activities. They were allowed to use the sensor to continue taking measurements afterwards. Long-term engagement is achieved by organising an initial activity that meets their needs.

Figure 12. Impressions of the activities for involving vulnerable groups.

General inhabitants & understanding heat stress in hot- and cool places

During Season 2 (summer 2025), we understood that with only analysing TRH data would not give the neighbourhoods the full understanding of how heat behaves in the built-up areas and how 'hot' and 'cool' places are actually perceived and used. Based on the experiences from Season 1/summer 2024 by our project partners in Dundee and Cascais, we developed a 'Thermal Perceptions Campaign' for Utrecht (see section 2. Thermal Perceptions Campaign for more information). Practically: doing surveys on the street, on designated perceived 'hot' or 'cool' places from Season 1. The same survey was also made accessible for people to answer the questions through a QR code made available on the website of Koele Buurt, Groene Buurt and through newsletters.

The Thermal Perceptions Campaign had a rather more 'social science' aspect, than the physical measurements and analysis from the TRH sensor data. For the analysis, interpretation and action planning in the 4 neighbourhoods, this information will provide a valuable reference (see section 2. Thermal Perceptions Campaign for more information).

Note: While not 'citizen science' per-se (surveys were made and done by civil servants from the partner organisations), this activity could have been done perfectly well by the local citizen communities. The insights will be merged into the analysis of the TRH data. Further elaboration of future activities will occur in early 2026, when outputs are processed and actions planned.

1.5 Findings and Reflections

Participation & data coverage

The Utrecht campaign produced a large and temporally rich dataset. After cleaning and merging measurement points, a total of 37,469 paired temperature and relative humidity observations were recorded within a 50 km radius of the city centre (Figure 13 shows the spatial coverage of these observations). These data were collected using 155 active devices between June and September in the years 2024 and 2025.

Figure 13. Spatial coverage of sensor measurements in Utrecht on a log scale.

Participation levels varied substantially between devices, with a small subset of participants contributing a disproportionately large share of the total observations. Figure 14 shows the amount of data collected by each device, ranked from highest to lowest. This reflects opportunistic data collection during daily routines such as commuting and leisure activities. Spatially, measurements are concentrated along frequently travelled routes and residential areas, producing dense clusters in high-activity zones and sparser coverage elsewhere.

Figure 14. Amount of data by device. (Counting a pair of relative humidity and temperature as one observation and ignoring the button records).

Observations in Utrecht are distributed across the full diurnal cycle, including morning, afternoon, evening, and nighttime periods. Figure 15 displays all temperature measurements collected in summer, overlaid over the same 24-hour cycle. Notably, a substantial fraction of measurements was collected during evening and nighttime periods. This temporal coverage strengthens the dataset's ability to capture urban heat island effects, particularly the persistence of elevated temperatures after sunset, which is less visible in campaigns dominated by daytime activity.

Figure 15. All temperature measurements throughout the days, with the median line and the 25 and 75 quartiles for each hour shown.

Temperature findings

Mobile sensors recorded temperatures ranging from 11.7 °C to 43.8 °C, with a median temperature of 25.1 °C across all observations. The wide temperature range reflects both seasonal variability and strong microclimatic differences at street level.

When compared with reference meteorological data, mobile sensor measurements in Utrecht are consistently higher. On average, sensor temperatures exceed reference station values by approximately 3.8 °C. This difference is smallest during daytime temperature peaks and becomes more pronounced during evening and nighttime hours, consistent with urban heat island dynamics.

Data quality & challenges

GPS inaccuracies are a recurring issue in the Utrecht dataset. Erratic positioning, as seen in the example of Figure 16 below, often occurs at the beginning or end of trips, likely caused by delayed GPS lock-on or signal obstruction indoors or near buildings. These artefacts can produce implausible movements or speeds exceeding typical walking or cycling behaviour. Such observations must be filtered or corrected prior to detailed spatial analyses. Speed distribution analyses show peaks around 1 km/h and 5 km/h, often associated with stationary periods during which GPS drift continues to record movement.

Figure 16. Example of a trip with dubious GPS records based on erratic measurements at the end of a trip, with speed in km/h.

Temperature measurement limitations

The mobile sensors lack standardized radiation shielding, making temperature readings susceptible to solar heating of the sensor casing. Sensor placement, orientation, and user behaviour introduce unobserved variability that can inflate recorded temperatures relative to true ambient air temperature.

The observed mean deviation of approximately 3.8 °C relative to reference stations likely reflects a combination of genuine street-level microclimatic conditions and systematic measurement bias.

Methodological considerations

The unstructured nature of citizen-generated mobile sensing data differs from traditional fixed-station or controlled transect approaches. Observations are collected along semi-random paths, at varying times, and under heterogeneous conditions. While this increases analytical complexity, the dataset remains valuable for characterising street-level thermal environments when supported by careful cleaning and modelling.

Hotspots and cool spots

Participants could mark locations as either a hotspot or a cool resting spot. A hotspot was indicated by pressing the button on the sensor or the discomfort button in the app. Cool resting spots could only be marked during the 2025 measurement summer, and exclusively via the app.

Table 1. Overview hotspots and coolspots based on button presses.

	Kanaleneiland	Ondiep	Rivierenwijk	Zuilen	Elsewhere
Hotspots	37	38	35	65	64
Cool spots	13	2	14	1	11

A combination of the above data and participants' personal insights resulted in the identification of 17 'hotspots' and 'cool spots' across the four neighbourhoods. These warm and cool locations were used in the thermal perception campaign as described in section 2. Thermal Perceptions Campaign.

Awareness & community

The effort to engage residents in the four neighbourhoods proved successful. Nearly equal numbers from Kanaleneiland, Rivierenwijk, and Ondiep/Zuilen showed interest: in 2024, 326 residents expressed interest, resulting in 103 active participants. In 2025, 85 residents signed up for *Groene Buurt*, *Koele Buurt*, and 61 sensors were distributed. These figures exclude additional participants involved through follow-up activities with community groups. This was a strong response, considering the specific topic, the call for active citizen science participation, and the diverse social composition of the areas.

News articles via local platforms like *Samen Meten Utrecht*, *BuurtNatuur030*, *RTV Utrecht*, as well as municipal and provincial channels broadened the audience for the Urban ReLeaf pilot activities. In addition, NMU organised neighbourhood-specific events focused on engagement and awareness: façade garden tours and neighbourhood safaris highlighted the link between urban heat stress and greening as a potential countermeasure, while offering shared activities for participants in the TRH campaign.

Although the data collected from the project is useful and valuable, participant engagement and awareness were primarily driven by strong community management. The app provided less feedback about heat and neighbourhoods conditions. However, by keeping participants informed through newsletters, the WhatsApp community, and organised activities, participants remained highly positive and engaged.

Shortly after distributing the first batch of sensors, it became clear that extensive technical support was necessary to ensure proper functioning of the sensors and the app. To address this, a helpdesk was set up. NMU, which initially received the technical questions, communicated effectively with ICCS to assist participants. A list of frequently asked questions was compiled and made available in the app during the second measurement summer.

Participants reported that the campaign significantly increased their awareness of heat stress and climate adaptation, highlighting temperature differences within neighbourhoods and the role of greenery and infrastructure. They valued contributing to a project that directly impacts their community, fostering connections with neighbours and a sense of shared responsibility. Many felt motivated knowing their efforts and collected data could inform future policy and tangible improvements for a greener, more liveable environment.

Figure 17 shows that 54% of participants indicated that they are considering taking measures to green their environment, while Figure 18 shows the variety of greening measures that participants are considering.

Overweeg je door dit project maatregelen te nemen om jouw omgeving te vergroenen of te verkoelen?

Figure 17. Graph showing the distribution of participants considering taking greening measures.

Zo ja, welke maatregelen overweeg je te nemen?

Figure 18. Graph showing which specific greening measures participants are considering.

A positive note from the participants: participating in the project lead do getting to know the neighbourhood better: getting to know more green spaces and better insights in the temperature.

A participant from Rivierenwijk:

“The measurements provided surprising insights. I didn’t realize that temperatures could vary so much within a single neighbourhood. Green spaces and trees really make a difference, but so do building shade, the type of paving, and even the number of parked cars. In some places, like near the water, it felt cool — but the sensor showed it was actually warmer there.”

A participant from the activity with SECU:

“Participating in this activity was a really positive experience for me. It felt good to contribute to something meaningful and beneficial for the community. I enjoyed being part of a project that raises awareness about heat stress and supports collective well-being.”

A participant of the Heat Crawl:

“I especially enjoyed being able to see the exact route I had walked using the app. I liked taking a slightly different route each time, which allowed me to discover many new places. In addition, while walking, I paid much closer attention to my neighbourhood — for example, I stopped to look at wall art that I normally cycle past, or I noticed things that contribute to (or help reduce) heat in the neighbourhoods I walked through.”

Evaluation 2024

At the end of the first year of the TRH campaign a survey was conducted under the participants. Most important conclusions:

What did you find most valuable about your participation?

1. Awareness of heat stress and climate adaptation:
 - Participants gained more insight into temperature differences within their neighbourhood and the factors that contribute to heat stress, such as buildings, green spaces, and paving.
 - The project demonstrated the urgency and relevance of climate adaptation for their living environment.
2. Neighbourhood involvement:
 - Many participants appreciated the opportunity to contribute to a project that directly affects their neighbourhood.
 - The initiative brought them into contact with neighbours and strengthened their sense of community.
3. Contributing to future improvements:
 - Participants felt part of a project with impact, aimed at a greener and more liveable neighbourhood.
 - The idea that the collected data could contribute to policy changes and concrete actions in the future was highly motivating.

Did participating in the measurement campaign provide you with any insights? If so, what insights?

1. Awareness of temperature differences:
 - There are large temperature differences within small areas of the neighbourhood.
 - Green areas and buildings noticeably influence the temperature.
2. Influence of the environment on heat stress:
 - Trees and shades provide coolness; a lack of them leads to higher temperatures.
 - Surprising warmth in places where coolness was expected, such as near water.
3. Confirmation of existing suspicions:
 - The campaign confirmed known hot spots in the neighbourhood.
 - Insights into how infrastructure and traffic influence the temperature.
4. Personal discoveries:
 - Discovered new streets and parts of the neighbourhood while measuring.
 - Became aware of my own walking behavior and distances.
5. Technical limitations:
 - Experiencing the difficulty of obtaining accurate temperature measurements.
 - Insight into the differences between the apparent temperature and the measured temperature.

Also, a lot of remarks were made about the problems with the sensor and the app. These remarks were shared with the project partners at the ICCS who were responsible for the app and the sensor.

Some additional suggestions were made about the campaign itself: Participants asked for more transparency of results and clarity of instructions. The first was addressed in 2025 by a participants-session about the data results. And these results were also sent to people who could not attend the meeting. Clarity of instructions was addressed by the instructions in meetings, WhatsApp community and in the app of the TRH campaign itself.

Enquête RIVM 2025

In 2025 RIVM did a questionnaire under the participants of the TRH campaign. The questionnaire was conducted at the beginning of the summer of 2025 and again in November 2025. 46 of the 61 participants replied.

Most important conclusions:

- The answers to the question: “*Resident involvement has made this research more relevant to me*” are in the *I agree a little bit* range (4.11) of the 5-point scale This is a very positive output.
- The answers to the question: “*Resident involvement has made this research more reliable for me*” is near the middle (3.63): agree-disagree. This is a bit less positive. We assume this is because of the problems with the sensors, but it could also be a sign that citizen involvement is not necessary to make research more reliable. We are thinking about getting some more answers to this topic by conducting lin-depth interviews with RIVM.

- The answer to the statement “*I trust the results of this research*” is again very positive. 4.13 (*I agree a little bit* range). So, the problems with the sensors did not result in the fact that the participants don’t trust the results.
- The participants expect results in greening the city, taking measurements against heat and creating cool spaces, spatial design.
- About 57% were positive about the influence the research will have on the policy of the government
- In the open questions is the most answered topic about the sensors. *Technical issues with sensor/app → frustrating, demotivating (By far the biggest theme): Sensor not working properly, connection issues with the app, routes were recorded incorrectly, problems increased in the second year, demotivating, made participation less enjoyable, reduced confidence in research results.*

From the participants we also heard that the inaccurate GPS led to long waits before they could set off. This may have resulted in them leaving the sensor at home and so less measurements.

Data analysis

Involving a data analyst in a citizen science project is crucial—not only for cleaning and making the data usable, but also for linking it with other data sources and identifying observations that lead to follow-up questions. A data analyst significantly contributes to better data collection, faster analysis and feedback, and drawing meaningful conclusions. For Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt, a data analyst has been involved since early 2025.

Information presentation

The feedback sessions during the campaign provided valuable insights but did not yet offer participants a clear course of action. Pop-up labs for storytelling and the development of local greening initiatives are essential to keep sharing the narrative on heat stress and climate adaptation and to maintain resident engagement. However, residents primarily seek the bigger picture: the impact of climate adaptation on their neighbourhood, practical options for action, and opportunities to collaborate with partners.

The campaign showed a shift in participant profile: more women and younger people joined, likely due to the emphasis on greening and community. Measurements confirm that local conditions sometimes differ significantly from models, such as higher temperatures along the canal and shade cooling houses rather than walkways. This highlights the importance of local observations and perceptions alongside data.

Key conclusions

Data models alone are insufficient for understanding urban environments, as perception and social factors play a crucial role alongside quantitative measurements. For example, areas identified as cool spots are not necessarily attractive or comfortable places for people to stay. While sensor measurements provide valuable information, the primary motivation for residents’ participation was often social interaction and the opportunity to engage collectively in greening efforts rather than the data itself.

For future policy, it is important to:

- Provide residents with a clear course of action.
- Integrate local insights into climate adaptation strategies.
- Secure budgets and concrete greening measures to prevent disappointment.

Possible solutions, action planning

With appropriate quality control and contextualisation, the Utrecht dataset can support urban microclimate modelling, cross-city comparative analyses, and studies of heat exposure and thermal comfort. Future deployments would benefit from improved sensor shielding, clearer participant guidance, and mechanisms allowing users to flag questionable data.

NMU is collaborating with the municipality on a proposal to design 12 city pergolas that provide cooling and greening. The locations and designs will be developed in collaboration with the community. Funding will be provided through a climate subsidy from the Province of Utrecht. The application will be submitted in January.

One of the derived results is the contribution to the Alexander Garden. This is a communal garden designed by local residents, constructed by the municipality of Utrecht, and maintained by them. The square is intended to become a vibrant place where it's pleasant to meet and enjoy the constant blooms. This is an example of how this project influences combining people and creating results.

A future step could also be to link with Utrecht Best Bemeten Stad (Utrecht Best Measured City). This is a collaboration among KNMI, RIVM and other partners to create a network of weather and air quality observations within the city. This is an ambition to realize this in the future.

Another further step is to contribute with the results to the revision of the Climate Adaptation Vision (planned in 2026) and conducting risk dialogues on heat stress.

Point of attention: a budget for implementing greening is essential in such a project.

We see a high risk of disappointing participants in a few years: if no concrete changes are made.

1.6 Recommendations and Future Steps

Future steps by the Utrecht municipality

We will use the collected information in a new version of the Utrecht City Climate Adaptation Vision. We will Inform the Municipal Council about insights of this project. We will use the information in the risk dialogues about heat with the inhabitants of the city.

We will actively involve the information in the programming of projects and supporting and prioritising neighbourhood initiatives.

We will try to keep the communities together: encouraging each other with opportunities and knowledge. We will link the communities to other projects, such as Waterproof 030.

Replicating or scaling the approach and making future campaigns more effective

The approach can be replicated in other citizen science work. Important is to keep people attached to the project by activities. But also, reliable technical equipment is an important factor to keep people attached. What worked was to inform people of the preliminary results.

2 Thermal Perceptions Campaign

In addition to the Heat Stress Campaign, we launched a perception survey in the four participating Utrecht neighbourhoods. We used a web-based survey which people could complete online, and the same survey was used to survey people on the street in several cool and hot spots with a paper version. A total of 164 surveys were completed.

2.1 Context and Objectives

The aim of the perception survey is to map the heat perception of residents and passers-by of 8 cool and hot spots. Later, new locations were added to it. In the TRH EcoPulse app it is not possible to give an indication of why a place is cool or heat in the opinion of the citizens. Next to data as humidity and temperature there are other factors that contribute to whether people say a place is a hotspot or a coolspot.

In addition to the TRH campaign the information collected will give us information on how people experience heat and which environmental factors in their opinion contribute to whether a place is experienced cool or heat.

These insights can be compared by the city of Utrecht with the perceived temperature map to see if the cool and hotspots align with the information we have.

The information will gain more insights into how cool- and hotspots are experienced and what factors are involved. This helps to make decisions on climate proof neighbourhoods. It also gives us information about how to combine different measurement-tools.

By adding a perception survey at observed hotspots (and coolspots) we want to work together with citizens to create inclusive policies and raise awareness regarding heat stress.

2.2 Design and Implementation

The following design and implementation were used in this part of the campaign.

Technology:

- Online website (Partimap) with survey questions and information
- Urban ReLeaf perception app on smartphone
- Local static information through plaque & QR code.
- Paper surveys

Target groups:

- Inclusive representation of the neighbourhoods
- In principle: all neighbourhood inhabitants in the public space during the summer pilot months.

Engagement:

- People in selected places are asked to share their perception of the place during hotter summer days. Those selected places were chosen with input from the participants of the TRH campaign.
- Live/online questionnaires
- Perception App surveys

Activities

- Design approach and synchronize with selection of places.
- Design questionnaires/surveys and prepare the technical tools, in corporation with RIVM
- Plan for summer campaign on 8 places (a 'hot' and 'cool' place in every neighbourhood)
- Halfway through the second measurement summer, new hotspots and cool resting places were added. In total, people could share their heat perception at 17 locations

Organisation

- Municipality and Province coordinated and organised, together with the other Utrecht partners.

As this is a separate part of the main TRH campaign, we made some changes to differentiate this part from the main TRH campaign. The following changes, which are reflected in Figure 19, were made:

- A separate logo is made for this part of the campaign. The logo of Groene Buurt Koele Buurt is adapted. Cooler colours were used.
- We used the title "Hitte in beeld" (Heat in the picture). As a subtitle we used "Hoe ervaar jij hitte en koelte in jouw buurt?" (How do you experience heat and coolness in your neighbourhood?)

Figure 19. The promotional leaflet used to draw attention to the survey.

Key partners & stakeholders

The first draft of the survey was made by RIVM. After that the municipality and province together finalised the survey together. After the first round of surveys more locations were added to the list, and the survey was updated (Appendix B: Second and final versions of the perception survey).

The survey was spread in the community of the main TRH campaign through the following channels to reach several groups:

- The community 'Green Neighbourhood, cool Neighbourhood' which also uses the TRH app through NMU
- Local neighbourhoods and community groups through the municipality
- Green newsletters through Buurtnatuur 030
- Several target groups through NMU
- Samen Meten Utrecht (Measuring Together Utrecht)

The Urban ReLeaf team of Utrecht municipality and province conducted paper surveys in person on several hot and coolspots on hot days of the summer weeks as shown in Figure 20. The survey respondents were depending on who was at the exact location on the time of the interviews. A banner was designed and used to attract attention to the survey team to promote engagement.

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE
EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Figure 20. Overview of the approach to the Thermal Perceptions Campaign.

2.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used

Partimap online survey

The Thermal Perceptions Campaign used a specially developed online questionnaire/survey webpage tool, Partimap, to process the answers given. Some of these questionnaires were done on paper and later submitted to the webpage.

We defined 17 specific sites in the same neighbourhoods (Ondiep, Zuilen, Kanaleneiland and Rivierenwijk) as the TRH campaign to conduct the surveys. These are cool spots and hot spots. The participants of the TRH campaigns contributed to choosing the sites which are mapped in Figure 21, and some pictures of several sites can be seen in Figure 22.

Figure 21. Map of the 17 survey sites identified as cool and hot spots.

We used surveys in Partimap for the citizens to use freely and paper surveys for the moments the team conducted the surveys and for the special target groups.

Figure 22. Thermal Perceptions Campaign survey activities.

2.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection

During summer 2025 we collected the perception data by letting people fill in the surveys on the Partimap online and by conducting passers-by. The aim is to indicate their perceptions on previously observed hot/cool spots that were identified by local residents and members of the TRH campaign as a hot space or a cool space. The answers to the survey will help to understand why places are experienced as heat or cool. Questions that were asked included:

- If it is a hot or a cool place
- What aspects (like sun, buildings, green etc.) contribute to if people experience the sites as cool or heat.
- Is this a place where you would prefer to stay more than 10 minutes.
- If there are other cool places people would prefer to stay in the area on a hot day.
- And several questions about the background of people.

The data will be used to get more understanding of why places are experienced as hot or cool. This background information will be used if policy is renewed or adapted, or if plans are made

for greening the city. For example, renewing the policy on climate adaptation is scheduled in 2026.

We have yet to analyse the results of the surveys. We are aiming on a meeting with the community early next year. We will share and discuss the results at that meeting. A summary of the results will also be sent at the participants of the THR campaign and to people who left contact information on the survey.

2.5 Findings and Reflections

We collected data from 164 surveys. 19 people, excluding existing participants from the Green Neighbourhood, Cool Neighbourhoods campaign, asked to keep them informed about the results. They will be invited for the community reflection on the data.

The collected data are not yet available, so we cannot say more about them. The data will be used by policymakers if plans are adapted.

Reflections on the results:

- The answers to the surveys depend on the weather. If it's not hot, the answer will be that it is a hot place.
- Several people answered that if it's a hot day they will seek cool in large cooled indoor shopping malls, not outside.
- The locations were all very different, not easy to conclude what makes a place a cool place where people want to stay when it is hot outside.
- The paper surveys conducted by the teams were conducted on weekdays during the holiday season. Locations were pretty empty of people. Maybe it is preferable to conduct surveys on weekends and/or outside the main holiday weeks.
- You get a better response result if a man tries to interview a man, and a woman a woman. So, the team had to be diverse.

2.6 Recommendations and Future Steps

We will discuss the data with the participants of the TRH campaign and with the people who want to stay informed. Results will be discussed with the climate adaptation policymakers of the city and considered if policy is renewed. They will also be shared among the projects aimed on greening the neighbourhoods of this project.

Ideal would have been to combine the TRH app with questions about perception. So that the data of the TRH app could be evaluated as why it was hot or cold. But this was technically not possible.

Another recommendation is to do more interviews, more in-depth interviews to really understand what people experience in hot and cool places would be relevant. Interviews on weekends and outside the main holiday weeks could be included to get better results.

References

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KNMI. (2010). *Warmte-eilandeffect van de stad Utrecht* (Heat island effect of the city of Utrecht). Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut (KNMI). Retrieved from <https://www.knmi.nl/kennis-en-datacentrum/achtergrond/warmte-eilandeffect-van-de-stad-utrecht>

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE
EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Appendices

Appendix A: User Agreement for participants Green Neighbourhood, Cool Neighbourhood

Gebruikersovereenkomst voor deelnemers Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt

Leuk dat je meedoet met **'Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt'**. Samen onderzoeken we hitte in je buurt en bedenken we oplossingen hiervoor. Door mee te doen ontvang je een draagbaar meetkastje. Het meetkastje is in bruikleen. Dat betekent dat je het meetkastje in bezit hebt, zonder dat het je eigendom is. Hiervoor maken we een paar afspraken:

Algemeen

- Het meetkastje meet luchttemperatuur en luchtvochtigheid op straat. Ook kan je jouw persoonlijk hittestress ervaring aangeven.
- Als je een sensor hebt die gekoppeld is aan je telefoon, dan kan je met een applicatie je persoonlijk metingen terugzien.

Verplichtingen van de deelnemer

- In de periode vanaf 1 juli t/m 30 september 2024 kan je metingen doen. Daarna dien je de sensor in te leveren bij Samen Meten Utrecht.
- Om in aanmerking te komen voor de VVV-voucher ter waarde van €40,00 gebruik je het meetkastje minimaal 10 keer, in jouw opgegeven wijk.
- Een meting bestaat uit een wandeling op straat, van minimaal 10 minuten. Natuurlijk mag je altijd langer of meer metingen doen.
- Probeer vooral op warme of hete momenten metingen te houden. Metingen kunnen zowel overdag als 's nachts gehouden worden.
- Behandel het meetkastje zorgvuldig en gebruik het alleen voor het beoogde doel.
- Bij schade, verlies of problemen, neem contact op via info@samenmetenutrecht.nl.

Privacy

- Jouw persoonsgegevens worden alleen gebruikt voor communicatie met jou over het meetproject, inclusief informatie over de bijhorende activiteiten.
- Jouw persoonsgegevens worden niet langer bewaard dan noodzakelijk is voor het doel van het project. Dat is tot uiterlijk 31-12-2028. Ofwel twee jaar na de officiële afronding van Urban ReLeaf, Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt.
- Wil je dat jouw persoonsgegevens worden gewist? Dat kan. Neem hiervoor contact op met info@samenmetenutrecht.nl
- Alle meetgegevens worden opgeslagen op een beveiligde server. Alleen meetgegevens die niet te herleiden zijn naar persoonlijke gegevens (zoals een woonadres) worden openbaar gesteld.
- Er is in Nederland een DPIA uitgevoerd (Data Protection Impact Assessment). Hierin zijn geen risico's voorzien voor deelname aan 'Groene Buurt Koele Buurt'. Wil je hier meer over weten, dan kun je contact zoeken met Samen Meten Utrecht via info@samenmetenutrecht.nl.

Beëindiging deelname

- Je kunt op elk moment stoppen met deelname door contact op te nemen met info@samenmetenutrecht.nl en het meetkastje terug te geven.

Naam:

Datum:

Handtekening deelnemer:

.....

Appendix B: Second and final versions of the perception survey

Beeldcredits: Michelle van Benschop

Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt:

Hoe ervaar jij deze plek op een warme dag?

Met het project Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt onderzoeken we hoe hitte wordt ervaren in de wijken Ondiep, Zuilen, Kanaleneiland en Rivierenwijk. We willen begrijpen waar het in de stad heet wordt, waarom dat gebeurt, en hoe groen de hitte vermindert.

Je staat op een locatie die door een andere Utrechter is gemarkeerd als een extra warme plek, óf juist een koelere plek.

We zijn benieuwd hoe jij het hier ervaart op een warme zomerdag. Door deze korte vragenlijst in te vullen, help je ons beter te begrijpen waarom bepaalde plekken als heet of koel worden ervaren. Zodat we er samen voor kunnen zorgen dat de stad in de toekomst ook tijdens warme dagen prettig blijft voor iedereen.

De vragenlijst is anoniem en het invullen duurt een paar minuten.

~ zie *privacy statement* aan het eind van het formulier ~

Doe mee en deel jouw ervaring!

DATUM	dd-mm-jjjj
TIJD	uu:mm
TEMPERATUUR	°C [evt. later uit KNMI data]
WIND	windkracht [evt. later uit KNMI data]

1. Waar zijn we op dit moment?

- Kanaleneiland: Attleeplantsoen/Spaaklaan
- Kanaleneiland: Spaaklaan/Peltlaan (nabij de speelplaats)
- Kanaleneiland: Kruispunt Van Heuven Goedhartlaan/Marshalllaan
- Kanaleneiland: Groenstrook tegenover Aziëlaan 18-22
- Kanaleneiland: Groenstrook tegenover Rooseveltlaan 694-726
- Kanaleneiland: Alexander de Grotelaan
- Kanaleneiland: Marcopolopark
- Rivierenwijk: kruispunt Waalstraat
- Rivierenwijk: Merwedekanaal/Gouwestraat
- Rivierenwijk: Kruispunt Spuistraat/Rijnlaan

- Ondiep: Thorbeckelaan (sportvelden)
- Ondiep: Schutstraat/Laan van Engelswier
- Ondiep: Kruispunt Anthoniedijk en Pijlstraat
- Zuilen: Edisonstraat/hoek Westinghousestraat
- Zuilen: Vechtzoompark (bij basisschool Wijzer aan de Vecht)
- Zuilen: Kruispunt Amsterdamsestraat - Sint Ludgerusstraat
- Zuilen: Kruispunt Amsterdamsestraat – Westinghousestraat

2. Hoe voelt het hier op dit moment?

- Te koud
 Lekker koel
 Niet warm, niet koud
 Lekker warm
 Te heet

3. Wat draagt bij aan WARMTE op deze plek?

...is dat door (meerdere antwoorden mogelijk):

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Zon? | <input type="checkbox"/> Geen wind? |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Bestrating? (asfalt, tegels) | <input type="checkbox"/> Verkeersdrukke, auto's? |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Bebouwing? | <input type="checkbox"/> Water in de buurt? |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Bomen en ander groen? | <input type="checkbox"/> Anders: |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Wind? | |

4. Wat draagt bij aan KOELTE op deze plek?

...is dat door (meerdere antwoorden mogelijk):

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Schaduw? | <input type="checkbox"/> Geen wind? |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Bestrating? (asfalt, tegels) | <input type="checkbox"/> Verkeersdrukke, auto's? |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Bebouwing? | <input type="checkbox"/> Water in de buurt? |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Bomen en ander groen? | <input type="checkbox"/> Anders: |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Wind? | |

5. Is dit een plek waar je voor langer dan 10 minuten naar toe zou gaan op een warme dag?

- Ja
 Nee
 Alleen als het moet

Waarom (niet)?

6. Op een hete dag, wat zijn dan koele plekken in deze buurt?

.....

Waar komt dat door?

.....

Mensen beleven hitte verschillend. De volgende vragen helpen om dat beter te begrijpen. Zodat we de stad op warme dagen zo comfortabel mogelijk kunnen maken voor iedereen.

7. Hoe oud ben je?

- | | | |
|--------------------------------------|--------------------------------|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Onder de 14 | <input type="checkbox"/> 25-34 | <input type="checkbox"/> 65-74 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 14-15 | <input type="checkbox"/> 35-44 | <input type="checkbox"/> 75 jaar of ouder |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 16-18 | <input type="checkbox"/> 45-54 | <input type="checkbox"/> Ik geef dit liever niet |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 19-24 | <input type="checkbox"/> 55-64 | aan |

8. Met welk geslacht identificeer je je?

- | | |
|--------------------------------|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Man | <input type="checkbox"/> Anders dan man of vrouw |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Vrouw | <input type="checkbox"/> Ik geef dit liever niet aan |

9. Is Nederlands jouw eerste taal of je moedertaal?

- | | |
|------------------------------|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Ja | <input type="checkbox"/> Ik heb meerdere moedertalen |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Nee | <input type="checkbox"/> Ik geef dit liever niet aan |

10. Wat is je opleiding?

- basisschool
- vmbo, havo, vwo of vergelijkbaar
- mbo, hbo, universiteit of vergelijkbaar
- Ik geef dit liever niet aan

11. Woon je in één van onderstaande wijken?

- Rivierenwijk
- Kanaleneiland
- Ondiep
- Zuilen
- ... ergens anders

12. Wat doe je in het dagelijks leven? (meerdere antwoorden mogelijk)

- Ik werk (betaald/vrijwillig) 32 uur of meer/wk
- Ik werk (betaald/vrijwillig) minder dan 32u/wk
- Ik werk op dit moment niet (bijv. vanwege ouderschapsverlof, of werkzoekend)
 - Ik ben met pensioen
 - Ik volg een opleiding
 - Anders, nml
 - Ik geef dit liever niet aan

13. Wil je op de hoogte blijven van *Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt*? Laat dan hier je emailadres achter:

Bedankt!

Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt is een samenwerking van de Natuur en Milieufederatie Utrecht, gemeente Utrecht en provincie Utrecht. Het project wil bijdragen aan betere lokale metingen/data, sterkere samenwerking tussen bewoners en overheden, en eerlijke klimaataanpak in de stad. In Utrecht richten we ons op wijken met relatief weinig groen. Meer informatie kan je vinden op: samenmetenutrecht.nl/project/koele-buurt

Groene Buurt, Koele Buurt is onderdeel van het Europese onderzoeksprogramma Urban ReLeaf. Urban ReLeaf loopt ook in Athene (Griekenland), Cascais (Portugal), Mannheim (Duitsland), Riga (Letland) en Dundee (Schotland). Meer weten over Urban ReLeaf? Kijk op urbanreleaf.eu

Foto: Michelle van Benschop

***** INFORMATIE OVER DE VERWERKING VAN PERSOONSGEGEVENS, VOLGENS VERORDENING (EU) 2016/679

Volgens Artikel 13 van Verordening (EU) 2016/679, informeren we je hoe persoonsgegevens worden verstrekt aan het International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) voor het Urban ReLeaf-project. Urban ReLeaf bevordert de samenwerking tussen lokale gemeenschappen en overheidsinstanties om huidige klimaatproblemen aan te pakken die verband houden met stedelijke groenplanning, hittestress en luchtvervuiling.

Verwerkingsverantwoordelijke

De verwerkingsverantwoordelijke is het International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Schlossplatz 1, 2361 Laxenburg, Oostenrijk.

Soorten verwerkte gegevens en doel van de verwerking

De persoonsgegevens die worden verstrekt bij het invullen van de enquête, of anderszins voor dit doel zijn verkregen, zijn: leeftijdscategorie, geslacht, opleidingsniveau, moedertaal, arbeidsstatus en locatie. Het verstrekken van deze gegevens is vrijwillig en dient voor onderzoeksdoeleinden naar hoe openbare plaatsen in Utrecht worden ervaren door bewoners tijdens warm weer en welke strategieën hun klimaatadaptieve transformatie kunnen ondersteunen.

Verwerkingsmethoden

Persoonsgegevens worden verzameld op een manier die directe identificatie van de betrokkene niet mogelijk maakt. Ze worden verwerkt met behulp van elektronische en papieren methoden via handelingen zoals verzameling, registratie, ordening, opslag, raadpleging, opvraging, gebruik, communicatie, verwijdering en vernietiging. Ze worden uitsluitend gebruikt voor geaggregeerde data-analyse door IIASA (Schlossplatz 1, 2361, Laxenburg, Oostenrijk), in het kader van de uitvoering van het Urban ReLeaf-project. De verwerking van gegevens door IIASA wordt uitgevoerd door personen die gemachtigd zijn door de verwerkingsverantwoordelijke en door degenen die door de verwerkingsverantwoordelijke zijn aangesteld, evenals door organisaties die namens de verwerkingsverantwoordelijke handelen overeenkomstig artikel 28 van Verordening (EU) 2016/679, als verwerkers, die handelen op basis van specifieke instructies met betrekking tot de doeleinden en methoden van de verwerking.

Bewaartermijn van gegevens

De gegevens worden bewaard door de verwerkingsverantwoordelijke gedurende de periode die nodig is voor de uitvoering van projectactiviteiten, en in ieder geval niet langer dan vijf (5) jaar.

Rechten van betrokkenen

Indien heridentificatie mogelijk is, hebben betrokkenen het recht om van de verwerkingsverantwoordelijke toegang tot, correctie, verwijdering of beperking van hun persoonsgegevens te vragen, of bezwaar te maken tegen de verwerking (Artikelen 15 e.v. van Verordening (EU) 2016/679). Dat kan door een verzoek in te dienen bij de verwerkingsverantwoordelijke via het volgende e-mailadres: hello@urbanreleaf.eu
